

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT
GPR	11	B		Min: 61.4575 Max: 62.5933	1406 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropropic

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: D 674-678, 1762-1763 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: *fill of construction cut for wall 5146*

Covered by SU: *0* Fills SU: *1407* Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (frequent, (m)edium, (r)are)

Anthropic	Geological	Organic
☒ Pottery <i>R</i> ☐ Nails ☒ Tiles <i>R</i> ☐ Marble ☐ Amphorae ☐ Quarried debris ☒ Dolia <i>R</i> ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Basalt slabs ☒ Mortar <i>M</i> ☐ Opus signinum ☐ Coins ☒ Painted plaster <i>F</i> ☒ Metal (specify) <i>R</i> ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Other (specify) ☐ Glass	☒ Tufo (specify) <i>F (small-medium irregular)</i> ☐ Travertine <i>R</i> ☐ Other Limestone ☒ Basalt <i>M</i> ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☒ Pebbles (range) <i>R (small)</i> ☐ Gravel (range)	☒ Charcoal <i>R</i> ☐ Ash ☒ Animal bones <i>R</i> ☐ Human bones ☒ Animal teeth <i>R</i> ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)

SOIL/MATRIX: clay *10%* silt *80%* sand *10%*
 Granular Layered Cohesive

Compaction	Color
☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☒ Loose ☐ Soft	☐ Black ☒ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to: _____ Is bound to (only for masonry): _____

Is abuted by: _____ Abuts: _____

Is covered by: *0* Covers: *5146*

Is cut by: _____ Cuts: _____

Is filled by: _____ Fills: *1407*

OBSERVATIONS: *includes soil compacted into wall 1058 above level of SU 1405*

DESCRIPTION: Position within sector: *Runs N-S along W. edge of arects. ends @ Southern edge*

Shape: *long, thin, irregular rectangle*

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): *slopes slightly to the south*

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): *no clusters. Artifact inclusions rare (except plaster)*

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): *Appears irregular, follows bedrock in depth*

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

Labels in sketch: *Tufa block*, *Construction cut SU 1407*, *SU 1405*, *Tufa slab SU 1404*, *Wall SU 1351*, *N*, *Vic Channel SU 1400*, *✓ = SU 1406*

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

The described material fills the construction cut of SU 1058, a wall of opus mixtum that runs all the way N-S from trench A into the "area urbana". Since the wall was a bench built feature, only the lowest part of the backfill within the construction cut is present and some soil that sticks against the wall an in between the stones. These material could also be the result of some later backfilling activities, it is not unlikely that a contamination with younger material is present in this SU's finds.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by T. Hart

Revised by CHM

PDFd by AMS

Entered by

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